

Transcription of Interview 3

*Shane Murphy
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Part 1:

Shane: ..views and perception of the National Health Insurance.

Interviewee 3: Okay.

Shane: So our first question, rather broadly, is, what do you think of NHI?

Interviewee 2: Just, you mean, overall, what it would mean?

Shane: Yes, what do you think of the idea, and the plans, and the overview of it; just your opinion?

Interviewee 2: Okay, well, basically, I think NHI is something, if achieved, would definitely help balance the health coverage that we have in South Africa. So I feel like it would definitely benefit the poorer South Africans in gaining access to services, quality services. So it will definitely be positive I think, if achieved.

Shane: Why do you say, if achieved?

Interviewee 2: If achieved, is because there are many steps, I think.. (connection problem) So we were saying, why, if achieved.

Shane: Yes.

Interviewee 2: Basically, there's many steps to be taken, I think, before we reach a system that (connection) Basically, there are many things that need to be in place, before we could say we've implemented NHI. There has to be a lot of change management, that will have to happen, in the department. As we all know, people are very resistant to change; anything that brings them out of their comfort zone. Changing the mindset of our staff, as well, in order to achieve; on top of system implementation, there's also change management and people management, that needs to happen, which is not always concentrated on, first, which it should be, if achieved.

Shane: Why do you feel that it should be concentrated on, first? Why do you think that human resources should be focused on, first?

Interviewee 2: A lot of the time, people are not consulted when introducing new projects in the department. I've recently, actually, just gone through a change management course, and I've learnt and seen the negative impact that has, on the project itself. So if we look at NHI as a new project we are implementing, onboarding of the staff that would have to work within the system, needs to happen. Consultation.. (internet interruption and recapping)

[05:41]

Shane: You said consultation..

Interviewee 2: Ja, basically, consulting and understanding what's happening on the ground.

Shane: And do you feel that that is something that's lacking in the..?

(bad connection, revert to phone conversation)

Part 2:

Shane: Continue where we left.

Interviewee 2: Yes, we were talking about the impact on the staff, basically.

Shane: Yes.

Interviewee 2: Ja, so [...] in my opinion, there hasn't been any onboarding of staff, in the department. Basically, we hear NHI from the media; we haven't really had people come in and talk to the people.. we're running all these solo projects, which are in [...] or reach a certain goal of NHI, but no one has really come through and say, okay, this is NHI, this is how we're going to go about implementing it, this is the project plan, this is where we are, this is where we need to be; nothing like that has ever happened in the department. It might have happened with our Chief Directors, but the operation of staff, never get that kind of information, yet the projects need to be implemented through them.

Shane: Why do you think that is, that they don't get the information?

Interviewee 2: Different reasons; most of the time, the information we've passed on, is high level meetings, that most of our operational managers are not part of; and maybe, then, there's a gap with communication between the senior management and the operational managers. Ja, but the information is not.. you don't get the total information, you get an introduction of **what you might do for their target**.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to receiving instructions, have you ever had an opportunity to provide input or feedback, around the policy, or its implementation?

Interviewee 2: Look, so I am part of the [...] **Society** of South Africa, and so when documents come out for comment, and things like that, then we are able to [...] to put our comments in, and they combine it and make a consolidated effort **to [...]**, towards NHI; so I have done that in the past. And through the [...], they've had a couple of meetings, where they try to explain what NHI means, and what would the **trauma [...]** be, in NHI, and how we would have to change our **role** in NHI; so we've had those discussions, through our [...].

Shane: Okay, that is separate from your job.

Interviewee 2: Separate from the department, ja, it is a private **organisation**.

Shane: Okay. And do you have any views on the strategic purchasing, proposed by the Bill, where they want to separate the funder from the provider? Do you think that's a good idea?

Interviewee 2: Agh, look, wherever money is involved, there should be proper governance, and obviously, money.. funding is going to be needed, and it needs to come from somewhere. I think the plan that they have in place would work, as long as it's governed properly.

Shane: Okay. And do you think that the infrastructure, currently available, to govern, is appropriate? Or would they need to bolster it?

Interviewee 2: Well, I definitely don't think that the **current** structure should govern it. And I'm not talking government [...], I'm talking, it should be, maybe, outsourced to a private company with people who have the expertise to govern, and to run the system for the department; it would work better that way.

Shane: Okay. So remove it from government's oversight?

Interviewee 2: Ja. Sort of like an auditor.

Shane: Okay yes, I understand that. And with regards to the current public service, would you say that the general health system is ready to implement NHI?

[05:04]

Interviewee 2: That's a [...] question. I think certain departments are ahead of others, so in terms of infrastructure, we might be behind, but if you look at things like our ideal clinic - I'm talking just, about Johannesburg - our ideal clinic, certain clinics have reached the status and have maintained it. We've got the CCMDD programme, where we've decongested a lot of people out of the facilities. So there are certain programmes that are **ahead** of each other, but obviously, the main thing being infrastructure, and whether we would be able to deal with.. we **can't** deal with the numbers that we have, **currently, there's where we are lucky.**

Shane: Okay. And what are your views on working with the private sector?

Interviewee 2: I think we definitely need each other, to provide, and to learn from each other as well. The private system is not perfect in all of its glamour and glory; they don't do so well in certain aspects, especially in things like ideal **hospitals**, many of them don't even comply; but in terms of governance, they would do much better. So I think they manage better, maybe, in terms of senior management, they manage better; their roles and responsibilities of people are clearer, there's more accountability in private. So those are the things, maybe, public sector can learn from, from private sector.

Shane: Okay. And what would you say, would be the best way to organise the public healthcare services, to implement and to contract, with the National Health Insurance? Do you have any ideas or opinions?

Interviewee 2: What would be the best way to?

Shane: Sort of organisation the public healthcare services? For instance, patient registries, or booking appointments, or making sure that patients go to primary clinics, first, or..?

Interviewee 2: Look, the department [your primary] healthcare setting into your first check, so I think a lot more work needs to be done in our primary healthcare clinic. If we had to look at a first step, I would say, going electronic is very much needed; we are still very paper-based. Then a whole lot of training needs to happen, [...] our clinicians and nurses are able to use the system, especially that we can start keeping track of our patients. Right now, we don't have any system to check our patients, so we're unable to quantify, or even qualify any of them.

Shane: Sure.

Interviewee 2: So you can't exactly plan for the numbers that you don't know.

Shane: Yes. And hopefully, NHI should be.. or phase three completed, at 2026; is that something that you can see happening?

Interviewee 2: Look, corona.. covid has set us back, quite a bit, and it's put a lot of pressure on our system at the moment. I'm not sure if we would reach the goal set out for 2026, but I know that there is progress every day, every financial year, there is progress towards reaching it. I'm not sure that we will reach it, depending on what covid continues to do to our system.

Shane: Yes. And what would you feel, are the biggest challenges, apart from what you have mentioned, the bigger challenges, to us successfully implementing the NHI?

Interviewee 2: I think there needs to be a lot more understanding of what NHI is. One of my main challenges is, even the private sector doesn't understand what NHI is. If you ask just a normal member of South Africa, like a citizen of South Africa, they don't understand what NHI is. If you look at it from the upper class, the richer people, they just think we are going to come and take from them. If you look at it from the medium class people, people earning an average salary, it will mean that they have to go use public facilities now. So nobody really understands what it is all about.

[10:40]

Shane: Yes.

Interviewee 2: So just as a general citizen of South Africa, I really think the department needs to do a lot more work, so that the citizens are also onboard, they can see what the government is trying to do. Because, really, if implemented, it can work, and it can help a lot of people, rich or poor or medium class. I mean, things like the medical aids, they do take advantage, they are overpriced, they are overcharging people; people are paying way too much for healthcare in South Africa. So it's not only going to benefit poor, it would definitely benefit the other types.

Shane: Okay. Then, Mrs Interviewee 2, from my side, that's all of my questions; is there any other opinion or view that you would like to express?

Interviewee 2: No, I think that's it. I hope I was able to answer your questions properly.

Shane: Yes, definitely. Thanks for the time. I know it was a difficult to get off.

Interviewee 2: [..] It's been really hectic, but thank you for making this arrangement.

Shane: Thanks so much, I hope you have a good day.

Interviewee 2: Okay, then, you too, bye-bye.

Shane: Bye.

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